

THE USE OF MODERN INTERNET TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the method of formation foreign language communicative competence based on modern Internet technologies. The relevance of the problem disclosed in the article is explained the growing need to use in the learning process more effective and varied means. The necessity is substantiated use of new types of electronic technologies of the second generation WEB 2.0 on the example of technology part of an organizer who only coordinates creative, academic students' activity.

Introduction

The process of globalization, the expansion of economic, social and cultural ties, the increasing freedom of movement, the need to master the skills necessary for communication and business in a multicultural and multilingual environment, have increased the educational value of learning foreign languages.

It is the knowledge of foreign languages that is one of the means of intercultural communication, that is, the totality of various forms of relations and communication between individuals and groups belonging to different cultures.

The problem of intercultural communication, due to objective reasons, has recently acquired special relevance and

demanding a revision of values and guidelines in the education system. The teaching of intercultural communication began to be considered not only from the position of learning the language itself, but also the culture of another country or countries. Undoubtedly, it is the language that occupies the first place among the nationally specific components of culture and can be both a means of communication and dissociation of people. The success of communication depends not only on the speaker's desire to make contact, but also on the ability to implement speech intention, which depends on the degree of proficiency in language units and the ability to use them correctly in specific communication situations. Thus, teaching foreign languages as a means of intercultural communication should be carried out simultaneously with the study of

the world and culture of the peoples who speak these languages. Knowledge of grammar rules and possession of a certain vocabulary is not enough for language proficiency. Theoretical knowledge should be complemented by practical skills: what, when, to whom and how to say.

In order to acquire such skills, it is necessary to study the world of the language, that is, the culture of the country in which the studied foreign language is spoken.

The use of modern Internet tools for the formation of communicative competence

The development of information and communication technologies has opened up new perspectives for teaching foreign languages. Their use facilitates and optimizes the process learning, helps to overcome the psychological barrier that arises among students when using a foreign language as a means of communication.

Today, we have at our disposal a number of tools that help create an atmosphere of immersion in an authentic language environment, penetrate into a different culture, realizing the principle of language functionality.

These tools, of course, include Web 2.0 services. Blogs, twitter, social networks, forums, wikis, audio and video casts have taken an important place in the process of learning a foreign language due to their accessibility in synchronous and asynchronous modes from any mobile device.

The advantages of information technologies used in the educational process are that, on the one hand:

- form and develop communicative language competence, which allows students to become participants in professional communication in a foreign language, to realize their professional needs and personal business contacts, to carry out professional self-education and improvement;
 - stimulate intercultural communication;
 - promote an intensive exchange of knowledge;
 - increase the motivation of students to study;
 - reveal the personal qualities, abilities, talents of students;
 - contribute to the development of skills of independent work.
- on the other hand, the use of Web 2.0 tools enables the teacher to:
- to speed up the process of formation of speech skills and language skills among students;
 - to interest students in the studied discipline;
 - to reveal the intellectual and creative potential of students;
 - to implement a more flexible individual approach to learning in accordance with the intellectual and speech capabilities of each student and the stage of teaching foreign languages.

In working with information technologies, the role of the teacher as an organizer and coordinator of the learning process is especially increasing.

Internet technologies provide ample opportunities for self-development and disclosure of the creative potential of the student's personality. They make it possible to work on educational material anytime, anywhere, synchronously or asynchronously with teachers and other students. Flexibility, individualization, interactivity, multimedia of the learning process using information technologies allow you to combine individual and group assignments. Modern Internet technologies open up wide access to educational services, making the learning process open and relatively inexpensive.

Using social language networks in teaching a foreign language

Among the Internet technologies related to communication and exchange or transmission of information, social language networks occupy a special place, since they are an instrument of live communication, direct linguistic contact with an interlocutor who is a native speaker of another language, another culture, historical tradition, social environment.

Educational social networks for learning foreign languages have recently gained wide popularity among people of different age groups and social status: student youth - students and schoolchildren, adults - working and housewives, business representatives, people of creative professions, doctors, lawyers, teachers and just naturally curious and sociable people. Thanks to the opportunity to communicate directly with people from other countries for free, we can learn more about the country of the interlocutor - life, customs, customs, habits,

national character and characteristics, national cuisine, people's views on various problems of everyday life. Live online communication with native speakers allows you to quickly remove the psychological barrier - to overcome the fear of communicating in a foreign language, improve your speaking and writing skills, replenish your vocabulary, speak the language, while saving time and money.

It should be noted that social language networks offer services designed for different categories of users, depending on the specific purpose of learning and the level of proficiency in a foreign language - from elementary situational communication on a tourist trip to a foreign country to fluency at the household level and professional communication. The fashion for educational social networks is growing all over the world, and in the future such networks will only develop both in the direction of increasing the number of participants and improving the quality of educational content, services and services offered by developers.

Conclusion

Social educational networks for studying foreign languages are constantly updated and improved - their interface is changing, new services are added, content is replenished, the quality of teaching methods is improving, the circle of participants is expanding. In the professional pedagogical community of many countries, they are seriously thinking about integrating social language networks into the educational process to increase the motivation of students to study, the formation and development of language

communicative competence, without which it is impossible to integrate into the modern information society.

Scientific and technological progress opens up all new opportunities, types and

forms of communication, the main condition for the effectiveness of which is mutual understanding, dialogue of cultures, tolerance and respect for the culture of communication partners.

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